

SELECTIVE METHYLATION OF QUINACETOPHENONE. A NEW
METHOD OF PREPARATION OF QUINACETOPHENONE
MONOMETHYL AND DIMETHYL ETHERS

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In connection with other investigations, quinacetophenone monomethyl ether was required in large quantity. The method of Kostanecki and Lampe (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 773) was found to be unsatisfactory as it led to the formation of a mixture of the mono- and dimethyl ethers, the yield of the monomethyl ether being considerably low. Kauffmann and Beisswenger (*Ber.*, 1905, 38, 789) obtained the monomethyl ether of quinacetophenone as a by-product in the Friedel-Crafts acetylation of quinol dimethyl ether. Baker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1922) prepared it by partial demethylation of quinacetophenone dimethyl ether. The above methods are not suitable for large-scale preparation and hence the present work was undertaken. The direct introduction of the acetyl group into the monomethyl ether of quinol was unsuccessfully tried by the Nencki as well as Hösch reactions, the unchanged monomethyl ether being recovered. Its Friedel-Crafts acetylation gave quinacetophenone in good yield, the demethylation occurring during the reaction. Similarly the Fries migration of its acetate resulted in the formation of quinacetophenone.

After several trials, it was found that the methylation of quinacetophenone by means of methyl iodide in acetone solution in presence of dry potassium carbonate could be satisfactorily effected, a good yield of its monomethyl ether being obtained (72%), without the contamination of the corresponding dimethyl ether.

Quinacetophenone Dimethyl Ether.—Quinacetophenone dimethyl ether has been prepared by various authors (Klages, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 3996; Kauffmann and Bleiswenger, *loc. cit.*; Kuroda and Matsukuna, *British Chem. Abs.*, 1932, 388) by Friedel-Crafts acetylation of quinol dimethyl ether.

A direct methylation of quinacetophenone by dimethyl sulphate has now been investigated and after several trials, a satisfactory method of preparing the quinacetophenone dimethyl ether in quantity (70-75%) has been evolved.

The results indicate that quinacetophenone can be methylated either to get exclusively its monomethyl ether or dimethyl ether according to the methylating reagent used. The advantage of the methods described here consists in getting the mono or dimethyl ether as required directly from quinacetophenone without the contamination of the other product.

Quinacetophenone Monomethyl Ether.—Quinacetophenone (30 g., 1 mol.) was dissolved in hot acetone (300 c.c., 10 parts) and to the cooled solution, anhydrous potassium carbonate (28 g., 1 mol.) and methyl iodide (40 g., 1.5 mols.) were added. The mixture was then refluxed on a water-bath (60°-70°) for 5 to 6 hours. Most of the acetone was then recovered by distillation. The thick residual liquid after acidifying

with dilute sulphuric acid was subjected to steam distillation. The milky distillate on cooling gave pale greenish yellow, long needles; they were collected and crystallised from hot water, m. p. $52-53^{\circ}$, yield, 18-20 g., 80% calculated on the amount of quinacetophenone utilised. It is easily soluble in common organic solvents.

The residue in the flask after steam-distillation was filtered hot. On cooling, the brown needles separated, m. p. 203° , identified as quinacetophenone (7 g.), which can be re-used for methylation.

Quinacetophenone Dimethyl Ether.—To a boiling solution of quinacetophenone (60 g., 1 mol.) in alcohol (300 to 360 c.c., 5-6 parts), dimethyl sulphate (120 g., 2.4 g. mols.) and hot sodium hydroxide solution (40 g. in 100 c.c. water) were alternately added in small instalments and the mixture well stirred. It took nearly half an hour. The reaction mixture was strongly alkaline throughout. It was then refluxed on a water-bath for two hours. Alcohol was then removed and the residue subjected to steam-distillation. The distillate was extracted with ether after adding salt to it. A thick oil was obtained after removing ether. It was dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 and distilled under reduced pressure, b. p. $156^{\circ}-158^{\circ}/15$ mm. yield, 50-52 g. (70-75%). The purified distillate solidifies on cooling in ice bath.

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